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Child Adoption in India-An Emerging Issue

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ABSTRACT

Adoption had hitherto been considered as a contested terrain in India. As an issue, there often exists some amount of hesitation in people's imagination for open deliberation. In other words, in social parlance, the approach to adoption in India has never been uniform everywhere: there are temporal and spatial variations. Presence of legal framework notwithstanding, the act of adoption is looked upon with grace at one place and disgrace at another place. Often, the way one relates to the act is replete with prejudice, superstitions and a priori notions. That renders the exercise contentious to comprehend the politics and polemics of child adoption. The present paper represents a modest endeavour to have a concise understanding of the issue at a conceptual level.

KEY WORDS: *Child Welfare, Domestic Adoption, Adoption Policy, Juvenile Justice, Illegal Adoption.*

INTRODUCTION

Child is the builder and molder of a nation's building. A Child having no biological parents or nearest relatives, is named as orphan, abandoned, destitute and worst of all an unknown entity in the society. In such circumstances, the child needs full care and protection from the society, which are its birthright. Recognizing the right, independent India assigned a prominent place to child welfare in the development plans of the country. Child welfare has today become one of the most important priorities not only in the field of social welfare but also in the other sector of development planning.

BACKGROUND

The concept of child adoption in India is known since time immemorial and the best ever adopted son was known as Lord "Krishna, who was adopted to "Nanda and Yoshada" though he was biological child of "Devaki and Basudev". However, it is a fact that the home is the best place for a child to grow in an atmosphere of love and affection and with maternal security. In fact, there could emotional, physical, intellectual and psychological

development of the child is possible. The child having no parents due to desertion, divorce and death, as such adoption is the best form of rehabilitating the child in a family instead of keeping such child under Institutional Care Services. Adoption therefore is defined as "the act by which the relation of paternity and affiliation is legally established between persons not so related of paternity and affiliation is legally established between persons not so related by nature". According to

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Wikipedia, “The act of adoption is defined as the legal process whereby a person assumes the parenting of another, usually a child, from that person’s biological or legal parent or parents”. In legal point of view, “adoptions permanently transfer all rights and responsibilities, along with affiliation from the biological parent or parents”. Adoption as defined is a human tendency to have a child whom one can call his own, bring him/her up for protection in old age, and heir to his property and to perpetuate the family name.

The Government of India has undertaken the National Children’s Policy for orphaned children by adopting several welfare schemes i.e. ICPS and recognizing the National Institute of Public Cooperation and Child Development (NIPCCD) etc. and also these efforts are being derived from the introduction of The National Policy on Children’s Right-1974; Prospective adoptive Plan on Child Welfare (1980-2000) and National Plan of Action for Child-1992; Ratification by India of the U. N. Convention on Rights of the Child in the early Nineties; preceded by SAARC concern for the Girl Children and the Government of India for Child Welfare.

Child adoption in India is governed by two primary laws: the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956 (HAMA) and the Juvenile Justice Act, 2015 (JJ Act). The Central Adoption Resource Authority (CARA) is the central body responsible for monitoring and regulating in-country and inter-country adoptions. Under HAMA, Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, and Sikhs are legalized to adopt children. This act provides relatively straightforward procedures for adoption. On the other hand, the JJ Act has more complex eligibility criteria for adoptive parents, requiring registration on CARA’s portal and a home study report by a specialized adoption agency. Recently, The Ministry of Women and Child Development said in its annual report for 2020-21 that 2.56 lakhs children were residing in the country’s 7,164 childcare institutions (CCIs). All these data prove the parity in the number of adoptions taking place in India and the number of abandoned children. CARA regulates the adoption of orphaned (parents have died), abandoned (parents have deserted), and surrendered (parents have legally given up custody) children through its affiliated or recognized agencies. 2021 Adoption (First Amendment) Regulations: It modifies the 2017 Adoption Regulations. The revision was notified per relevant provisions of the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015 (2 of 2016), and it

modifies the Adoption Regulations, 2017. The parliament passed Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Amendment Act, 2021, aims to tighten and streamline rules for child protection. It specifies that, rather than the court, such adoption orders shall be issued by the District Magistrate (including the Additional District Magistrate). Additionally, CARA maintains a database of children and registration of prospective parents on a centralized Child Adoption Resource Information and Guidance System (CARINGS).

In January 2023, the Bombay High Court issued a directive that caused confusion in the adoption process. It instructed the state government not to transfer pending adoption proceedings to District Magistrates, as mandated by the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Amendment Act, 2021. This raised concerns about the potential hindrance to progress in resolving adoption cases. However, there have been positive developments as well. The Adoption Regulations-2022, introduced by the Ministry of Women and Child Development, aimed to streamline the adoption process. District Magistrates (DMs) and Child Welfare Committees were instructed to upload adoption orders and case status in real time. Since the implementation of these regulations, 2,297 adoption orders have been issued by DMs nationwide, making significant progress in resolving pending cases

Major Challenges Related to Adoption in India:

- a). Lengthy and Complex Adoption Process: -The adoption process in India can be excessively bureaucratic and time-consuming. Data from CARA indicates that over 30,000 prospective parents are currently waiting to adopt, while only 2,131 children are legally free for adoption. Moreover, around two-thirds of these children have special needs, and it takes an average of three years for the adoption process to be completed.
- b). Illegal and Unregulated Practices: -There have been disturbing instances of illegal adoption practices in India, including baby trafficking and child-selling.
- c). Returning Children after Adoption: - India has seen a troubling trend of adoptive parents returning children after adopting them. In 2020, CARA reported that over 1,100 children adopted across the country had been returned to child care institutions by their adoptive parents in the last five years.

Suggestions & Conclusion

- i) **Strengthening Adoption Laws:** -India needs to review and update adoption laws to streamline the process, making it more transparent and efficient. This could involve simplifying paperwork, reducing delays, and addressing any ambiguities or loopholes in the existing legislation.
- ii) **Post-Adoption Services:** -Comprehensive post-adoption support services should be established to assist both adoptive parents and adopted children. These services might include counselling, educational support, access to healthcare, and guidance for managing challenges that may arise during the adoption journey.
- iii) **Awareness and Education:** -Promoting awareness about adoption as a viable option for building families is crucial. This includes educating the public about the benefits, procedures, and legal aspects of adoption. It's essential to encourage positive attitudes towards adoption and dispel misconceptions or stigma associated with it.

However, several challenges, including a complex process and illegal practices, need to be addressed. Recent developments, such as the Adoption Regulations-2022, show promise, but there is a pressing need for further reform to ensure that the best interests of the child are upheld throughout the adoption journey.

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